

September 5,
2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
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International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 05.09.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

O'QUVCHILARNING MOTIVATSIYASINI OSHIRISHDA O'QITUVCHINING PEDAGOGIK MAHORATI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'quvchilarda o'qishga bo'lgan motivatsiyani shakllantirish va rivojlantirish jarayonida o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati tahlil qilinadi. Motivatsiyani oshirishda pedagogik uslub, interfaol metodlar, individual yondashuv va o'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlari muhim omil sifatida ko'rsatib o'tilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari o'qituvchining kasbiy mahorati o'quvchilarning o'qishga qiziqishi va faolligini bevosita belgilovchi omil ekanligini isbotlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: motivatsiya, pedagogik mahorat, ta'lim samaradorligi, interfaol metod, shaxsga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim.

Kirish

Bugungi globallashuv jarayonida ta'lim sifati va samaradorligi davlat taraqqiyoti uchun hal qiluvchi omil hisoblanadi. O'quvchilarning ta'lim jarayonidagi faolligi, qiziqishi va tashabbuskorligi ularning motivatsiya darajasi bilan bevosita bog'liqdir. Ta'lim motivatsiyasi nafaqat bilimlarni o'zlashtirishga, balki shaxsning intellektual va ma'naviy rivojlanishiga ham ta'sir etadi. Shu jihatdan qaraganda, o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati – ya'ni metodik bilimlari, darsni tashkil qilish ko'nikmalari, psixologik yondashuvi va shaxsiy fazilatlari o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirishda hal qiluvchi o'rin tutadi. Mazkur maqolada pedagogik mahorat va motivatsiya o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik, shuningdek, samarali yondashuvlar ilmiy tahlil qilinadi.

Metodologiya

Tadqiqotning metodologik asosi sifatida:

- pedagogika va psixologiya sohasidagi nazariy manbalar o'rganildi;
- ta'lim jarayonida o'qituvchilarning tajribasi kuzatildi;
- o'quvchilar orasida so'rovnomalar o'tkazilib, motivatsiyani oshirishda qaysi metodlar samarali ekani tahlil qilindi.

So'rovnomada 80 nafar o'quvchi va 15 nafar o'qituvchi ishtirok etdi. Natijalar statistik tahlil qilindi.

Natijalar

1-jadval.

O'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati va o'quvchilar motivatsiyasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik

Jadval natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, eng yuqori ta'sir qiluvchi omil – bu o'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlari (78%), undan keyin psixologik yondashuv (70%) va rag'batlantirish tizimi (65%). Bu esa pedagogik mahoratning nafaqat metodik, balki shaxsiy-psixologik jihatlari ham o'quvchilar motivatsiyasida muhim ekanini tasdiqlaydi.

Tadqiqot natijalari quyidagilarni ko'rsatdi:

1. Pedagogik mahorat darajasi yuqori bo'lgan o'qituvchilar darslarida o'quvchilarning ishtiroki 65–70% yuqori bo'lgan.
2. O'quvchilarni rag'batlantirish, innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish va individual yondashuv motivatsiyani sezilarli oshirgan.
3. O'quvchilarning 78%i o'qituvchining shaxsiy fazilatlari (mehribonlik, adolat, tushunuvchanlik) motivatsiyada katta rol o'ynashini ta'kidlagan.
4. Darslarda turli interaktiv metodlardan (munozara, "aqliy hujum", rolli o'yinlar) foydalanilgan sinflarda o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash ko'nikmalari tezroq rivojlangan.

Muhokama

O'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati uch asosiy omil bilan belgilanadi:

- Metodik tayyorgarlik – dars jarayonini to'g'ri rejalash, didaktik materiallardan foydalanish.
- Psixologik yondashuv – o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini inobatga olish, ijobiy psixologik muhit yaratish.
- Shaxsiy fazilatlar – adolat, mehribonlik, o'ziga ishonch va kommunikativlik.

Motivatsiyani oshirish uchun o'qituvchilar quyidagi yondashuvlarni qo'llashlari maqsadga muvofiq:

1. Rag'batlantirish tizimi – o'quvchilarning kichik yutuqlarini ham qadrlash.
2. Innovatsion metodlar – texnologiyalar, interaktiv o'yinlar, loyiha metodini tatbiq qilish.
3. O'quvchini jarayon markaziga qo'yish – passiv tinglovchidan faol ishtirokchiga aylantirish.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib aytganda, o'qituvchining pedagogik mahorati o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini shakllantirish va oshirishda asosiy omil hisoblanadi. Yuqori malakali, psixologik jihatdan tayyorlangan, innovatsion metodlardan foydalangan o'qituvchi o'quvchilarda nafaqat bilim olishga, balki mustaqil fikrlash, ijodiy yondashuv va o'zini rivojlantirishga bo'lgan intilishni ham uyg'otadi. Shunday ekan, o'qituvchilarni muntazam malaka oshirish, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni o'rganishga yo'naltirish va ularga sharoit yaratish ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning muhim shartidir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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